

Thin Layer and Column Chromatographic Separations of Isomers of some Metal Complexes of Isonitroso Ligands

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Thin layer and column chromatography techniques have been employed for the detection and separation of isomers of metal complexes of isonitrosothiocamphor with Co^{III} , isonitrosoacetophenone with Co^{III} and Pt^{II} , isonitrosoacetylacetone with Pt^{II} and an imine derivative of its Ni^{II} complex. Electronic and/or ir spectral studies of the separated components have been made.

A number of transition metal complexes with various isonitroso ligands have been synthesised and their structures investigated by magnetic and spectral methods. Isonitroso compounds are potentially ambidentate ligands capable of forming metal complexes with a variety of structures/bonding. The metal complexes of this type of ligands are therefore expected to contain isomers, the detection and separation of which could be interesting. In fact, spectral studies of imine derivative of Ni^{II} complexes of isonitrosoacetylacetone¹, $\text{Ni}(\text{INAA})_2$ and Co^{III} complex of isonitrosothiocamphor², $\text{Co}(\text{INTC})_3$, have shown the

possibility of existence of two or more isomers, at least in solution, for these complexes. Also, two coloured varieties, light-green and brown, of Ni^{II} complex of isonitrosoacetophenone³ (HINAP) and *cis*- and *trans*-isomers of Pd^{II} complex of isonitrosoacetylacetone⁴, $\text{Pd}(\text{INAA})_2$, have been reported. Recently, chromatographic techniques have found widespread use in investigation of different areas of chemistry of metal complexes^{5,6}.

In the present studies, thin layer (tlc) and column chromatographic techniques have been used for detection and separation of isomers of the metal complexes of isoni-

TABLE I—SEPARATION OF METAL COMPLEXES BY TLC AND COLUMN CHROMATOGRAPHY (CC)

Compound (Colour)	Solvent for tlc	Colour of the separated component on tlc	R_f	Developing solvent for cc	No. of components separated on column	R_f of fraction separated on column	Column capacity (ml)	Amount of silica gel used for column (g)
$\text{Co}(\text{INTC})_3$ (Dark-red)	Benzene	(i) Pink	0.125	Petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80) followed by benzene	Two	(i) 0.125	40	15
		(ii) Pink	0.083			(ii) 0.083		
$\text{Co}(\text{INAP})_3$ (Orange-red)	Chloroform	(i) Yellow	0.270	Benzene followed by chloroform	Two	(i) 0.270	135	400
		(ii) Yellow-orange	0.160			(ii) 0.160		
$\text{Pt}(\text{INAP})_2$ (Dark-brown)	Benzene	(i) Yellowish green	0.500	Benzene	Three	(i) 0.500	30	10
		(ii) Reddish brown	0.330			(ii) 0.330		
		(iii) Violet	0.160			(iii) 0.160		
		(iv) Brownish green	0.080					
$\text{Pt}(\text{INAA})_2$ (Brown)	Ethyl acetate-acetone (9 : 1)	(i) Violet	0.930	Benzene followed by ether	Three	(i) 0.930	50	20
		(ii) Green	0.750			(ii) 0.750		
		(iii) Brown	0.420			(iii) 0.420		
$\text{Ni}(\text{INAAI})_2$ (Orange-red)	Ethyl acetate	(i) Orange	0.930	Benzene	Four	(i) 0.930	50	20
		(ii) Orange-yellow	0.860			(ii) 0.860		
		(iii) Yellow-orange	0.760			(iii) 0.760		
		(iv) Yellow	0.650			(iv) 0.650		

trosothiocamphor (HINTC), isonitrosoacetophenone (HINAP) and isonitrosoacetylacetone (HINAA), viz. $\text{Co}(\text{INTC})_3$, $\text{Co}(\text{INAP})_3$, $\text{Pt}(\text{INAP})_2$, $\text{Pt}(\text{INAA})_2$ and an imine derivative of Ni^{II} complex of isonitrosoacetylacetone¹, $\text{Ni}(\text{INAAI})_2$. Electronic and/or ir spectra of the separated components of the complexes have also been studied.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the results of tlc and column chromatographic studies of the metal complexes. The results indicate the presence of two or more components in all the complexes. Thus $\text{Co}(\text{INTC})_3$ and $\text{Co}(\text{INAP})_3$ could be resolved into two components each, while $\text{Pt}(\text{INAP})_2$ and $\text{Pt}(\text{INAA})_2$ could be separated into four and three components respectively. Similarly, $\text{Ni}(\text{INAAI})_2$ can also be resolved into four components.

Attempts were made to separate the complexes by column chromatography. The results (Table 1) indicate that $\text{Co}(\text{INTC})_3$, $\text{Co}(\text{INAP})_3$, $\text{Pt}(\text{INAAI})_2$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{INAA})_2$ could be separated into their components. However, $\text{Pt}(\text{INAP})_2$ which resolved into four components on tlc plates, could be separated into only three fractions corresponding to R_f values of 0.50, 0.33 and 0.16. The fourth fraction corresponding to R_f value of 0.08 could not be separated probably because of its very low mobility.

Table 2 summarises the electronic absorption and ir spectral bands exhibited by the two components of $\text{Co}(\text{INTC})_3$ separated on column. The spectral features are in agreement with the octahedral low-spin Co^{III} configuration as suggested by the diamagnetism of the complex. The ir spectra of two components do not show any band at 3 200–3 600 cm^{-1} , indicating the absence of OH group and presence of five-membered ring structure for these components. In addition, component-one show a sharp peak at 1 345 and a sharp doublet around 1 370–1 390 cm^{-1} , while fraction-two exhibits only a broad band at 1 345 cm^{-1} .

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC AND INFRARED SPECTRAL BANDS OF $\text{Co}(\text{INTC})_3$ AND THEIR ASSIGNMENTS

Spectral	Component-I ($R_f = 0.125$)	Component-II ($R_f = 0.083$)	Assignment
Electronic spectra (cm^{-1})	40 360 ($\epsilon \sim 23\ 180$)	40 800 ($\epsilon \sim 14\ 400$)	$\pi-\pi^*$
	33 900 ($\epsilon \sim 47\ 650$)	33 900 ($\epsilon \sim 15\ 700$)	$\pi-\pi^*$
	31 250 ($\epsilon \sim 45\ 300$)	30 800 ($\epsilon \sim 18\ 500$)	$\pi-\pi^*$
	19 610 ($\epsilon \sim 39\ 100$)	19 610 ($\epsilon \sim 2\ 120$)	Charge transfer
	10 100 ($\epsilon \sim 6.6$)	10 200 ($\epsilon \sim 3.4$)	$d-d$
	Infrared spectra (cm^{-1})	1 420	1 425
1 090		1 080	N \rightarrow O
955		955	C=S
525		535	M-N

The reflectance spectra of two components show two bands at 27 780 and 25 640 cm^{-1} for component-two ($R_f = 0.16$) but only one broad band at 26 320 cm^{-1} for component-one ($R_f = 0.27$). The solution spectra show consistently high values for component one.

Ir spectra of the components of $\text{Pt}(\text{INAP})_2$ (Table 3) indicate absence of OH group, coordination through carbonyl oxygen and presence of N \rightarrow O stretching frequency. It is reported to have five-membered chelating ring structure making it necessary to consider structure (II)⁸. Component-

one and -three can be presented as *cis*- and *trans*-isomers with structure (II), which would explain the presence of bands in the region 1 600–1 700 cm^{-1} due to C=C stretching vibrations. As component-three exhibits more bands it may be *cis* as also the higher ϵ values⁹ observed for many platinum complexes¹⁰⁻¹².

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC AND IR SPECTRA OF $\text{Pt}(\text{INAP})_2$

	Component I ($R_f = 0.50$)	Component II ($R_f = 0.33$)	Component III ($R_f = 0.16$)
ν_{max} (cm^{-1}):			
1 300–1 400	Two bands weak and medium	Two bands weak and medium	No band
1 660–1 670	One band	No band	One band
λ_{max} (cm^{-1}):			
20 000	No band	Max. at 20 000	Max. at 23 260
23 260	band		

Table 4 gives electronic spectral data of three components of $\text{Pt}(\text{INAA})_2$ and is suggestive of square-planar geometry and indicates that they are not identical. $\text{Pt}(\text{INAA})_2$ may have the similar structure as $\text{Pt}(\text{INAP})_2$.

The orange red $\text{Ni}(\text{INAAI})_2$ compound shows from pmr studies, the existence of at least three isomers (structures III and IV). The complex can be resolved into four components and their electronic spectra in benzene exhibit a maxima and a hump near 28 990 and 20 830 cm^{-1} respectively. Table 5 gives the molar absorptivities of the four components at the two wavelengths.

TABLE 4—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA (cm^{-1}) OF $\text{Pt}(\text{INAA})_2$

Component I ($R_f = 0.93$)	Component II ($R_f = 0.75$)	Component III ($R_f = 0.42$)
38 460 ($\pi-\pi^*$)	—	—
32 260 weak hump	—	32 260 hump
22 220 hump (C.T.)	23 250– 25 000	23 250– 25 000 hump (C.T.)
1 660 —	— 1 340, 1 260 965, 920	— 1 110 medium intensity
670 strong shoulder	670 weak doublet	670 weak singlet

The ir spectra of component one and two, and that of component three and four are similar. The presence of strong band near $3\ 300\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of component one and two is then in accordance with non-coordinated N–H stretching frequency, whereas the less intense N–H band at $3\ 280\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ in spectra of component three and four could be due to stretching vibrations of coordinated –NH group.

TABLE 5—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA (cm^{-1}) OF $\text{Ni}(\text{INAA})_2$

Fraction	R_f	ϵ at	
		$28\ 990\ \text{cm}^{-1}$	$20\ 830\ \text{cm}^{-1}$
(i)	0.93	10 300	1 240
(ii)	0.86	17 000	1 920
(iii)	0.76	36 300	4 330
(iv)	0.65	15 300	1 720

Experimental

Most of the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. C.P. grade chemicals were used after purification by standard methods.

The ligand HINTC^{13} , HINAP^{14} and HINAA^{14} were prepared by the reported procedures. The metal complexes $\text{Co}(\text{INAP})_3^7$, $\text{Pt}(\text{INAP})_2^3$, $\text{Co}(\text{INTC})_2^2$, $\text{Pt}(\text{INAA})_2^1$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{INAA})_2^1$ were prepared by the recommended procedures.

Preparation of $\text{Co}(\text{INTC})_3$: A filtered, alcoholic solution of HINTC was added to an aqueous solution of Co^{III} in

the ratio 3 : 1. The dark red coloured complex separated, washed with water, dried at 105° and crystallised from benzene.

Preparation of $\text{Pt}(\text{INAA})_2$: An aqueous solution of HINAA was added to a faintly acidic solution of platinum(II) chloride in water in 2 : 1 proportion. The mixture was digested on a hot water-bath for ~30 min. The brown coloured complex separated was washed with water and dried at 105° .

Tlc studies of the metal complexes were carried out with an ACME chromatographic equipment (India). Water-based slurry of silica gel (type 60, CaSO_4 binder) was used to prepare tlc plates (10×20 or 20×20 cm). The complex components separated could be detected directly by their characteristic colours or by placing the plates in an iodine chamber. Column chromatographic studies were carried out with an Emenvée automatic fraction collector using columns of varying capacity, with silica gel as adsorbent. Different fractions collected were run on tlc plate to check the purity of the components being separated.

The electronic and reflectance spectra were measured on a CZ-VSU-2P spectrophotometer and ir spectra on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer.

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